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Histeridae: *Hololepta australica*

Histeridae: *Pactolinus caffer*

Histeridae: *Teretriosoma* sp.

Hydrophilidae: *Coelostoma* sp.

Cut reduced

This fusion is indicated
 by Cupedidae: *Priaema*

Hydrophilidae: *Helophorus lacustris*

Hydrochidae: *Hydrochus* sp.

Hydrophilidae: *Hydrophilus latipalpus*

HYDROPHILIDAE: *Hydrophilus*

Hydrophilidae: *Hydrophilus* sp.

DORSAL

VENTRAL

Hydrophilidae: *Limnoxenus*

HYDROPHILIDAE: *Pseudohydrobius*

HYDROPHILIDAE: *Rygmodes modestus*

rare plesiomorphy: Cut retained!
 shows clearly RA₃, RA₄, fusion of RA₂ RP₁₊₂, branching RP₁₊₂ and RP₃₊₄
 and shows MA as independent vein from RP

Sphaeridiinae

HYDROPHILIDAE: *Dactylosternum* sp.

Spercheidae: *Spercherus* sp.

Sphaeritidae: *Sphaerites glabratus*

Synteliidae: *Syntelia mexicana*

- ① R+MA fusion = synapomorphy of Blatto + Hemi + Holoneoptera
- ② Absence of Cu stem = plesiomorphy (or very short?) (important!)

Example of: membranous PC
 separate existence of Cc
 SCA bulge superimposed
 good B Sc
 very good long CuP

Synteliidae: *Syntelia mexicana*

Agyrtidae: *Necrophilus* sp.

Agyrt. *Necrophilus hydrophiloides*

(17)

Sistergroup of Scarabs?

cr = mp - cua cross-vein = Endopterygota apomorphy

Presence of AP₁₊₂ - plesiomorphic within Coleopt.

Staphylininoidea: Hydraenidae "Metropatus" sp.

Hydraenidae: *Parhydraenia* sp.

Leiodidae: *Eublackburniella* sp. nipple present

Silphidae: *Diamesus* sp.

Silphidae: *Ptomaphila lacrymosa*

no embayment at anal fold strange

Staphylinidae: *Austrolaphrum australe*

radial cell very narrow,
elongate, hipple present

aberrant radial cell...
RP & MA & MP 1+2 fused

Staphylinidae: *Creophilus erythrocephalus*

Staphylinidae: *Creophilus erythrocephalus* wing base

Staphylinidae: *Creophilus*

DORSAL

VENTRAL

Staphylinidae: *Priochrus mites*

Coleoptera apomorphies in hind wing articulation:
 AX-PC & C (tegula) reduced; B-R partly membranized; F-M subdivided; B-M large, connected with B-Cu; AX-Cu (3Ax) small, sutured, and often fragmented; AX-Cu fused with F-Cu; F-Cu fused with FA

Staphylinidae: Sartallus sp.

radial cell - no nipple (reduction)

Staphylinidae: *Scaphidium* sp.

Staphulinidae: *Baeocera* sp.

Ceratocanthidae: *Cloeotus aphodioides*

Ceratocanthidae: *Cloeotus aphodioides*

Diphyllostomatidae: *Diphyllostoma*

Diphylostomatidae: *Diphylostoma*

Geotrupidae: *Elaphostomus probosideus*

medial F subdivided!

interpret. of 3Ax is tentative.
(study more spec)

- Example of:
- ① FR in 2Ax very weak (missing in Frickia)
 - ② the existence of a member, window + weak sutures between the artic. sclerites which composed 3Ax
 - ③ very large head of 1Ax
 - ④ reduced pr. ball of med. plate

Geotrupidae: *Elaphostomus probosideus*

Geotrupidae: *Elephastomus proboscideus*

Geotrupidae: *Elephastomus proboscideus*

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Geotrupidae: *Frickius* sp.

Misc FR from 2AX as
Scarabaeidae! Sisters group?

lower part of $\mu 2$ is lost but a niple on R shows
where it originally attached

radial cell seems primitive
so does RP 3+4 & MP 1+2
so does RA 4 & RP 1
so does AP 1+2 pectinat

Geotrupidae: *Frickius*

17.8

Orphidae: *Goniorphus felschei*

Cut is in claval line (shortened)
 very similar to *Phaenognatha brichsoni*...

Glaphyridae: *Amphycoma bombylifformis*

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Glaphyridae: *Amphycoma bombylifformis*

Glaresidae: *Glaresis walzae*

Scarab
Glaresidae
Glaresis walzae
♂
Sudan

6 mm length

This is the most primitive scarab wing, more so than *Trox*.
 Primitive: radial cell (at scarabid level)
 nearly Δ fold into which radial cell is pushed (at Polyphaga level)
 weak AA1+2 present (the only case known to me in Scarabaeoidea!)

Derived: fusion of RA4 + RP1 (in *Trox*, Lucanidae, etc. RA4 and RP, run close but are not fused)
 (probably apomorphic higher than genus)
 veins completely reduced } weak charact - species? smaller size? derived? etc?
 base of RA4 lost

Glaresidae: *Glaresis walzae*

Hybosoridae: *Phaeochrous emarginatus*

DORSAL VIEW

VENTRAL VIEW

Hybosoridae: *Phaeochrous emarginatus*

Structure of radial hinge

Hybosoridae: *Phaeochrous emarginatus*

Lucanidae: *Aesalus scarabaeoides*

Lucanidae: *Lamprima* sp.

Lucanidae: *Lamprima* sp.

precostal strip

Lucanidae: *Synoesus cornutus*

Passalidae: *Aulacocyclus edentulus*

Coleo: Passalidae: *Popilius disjunctus*

Coleo: Passalidae *Popilius disjunctus*

Pleocomidae: *Pleocoma behrensi*

Scarabaeidae: *Cryptodus paradoxus*

Scarabaeidae: *Cryptodus paradoxus*

Scarabaeidae: *Cryptodus paradoxus*

Scarab: *Cryptodus paradoxus*

Scarabaeidae: *Goniorphinus felchei*

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Scarabaeidae, Orphninae: *Goniorphinus felschei*

Cut is in claval line (shortened)
very similar to *Phaenognatha brichsoni*...

Scarabaeidae: *Phaenognatha erichsoni*

Histeroidea
Synteliidae: *Syntelia mexicana*

Synteliidae: *Syntelia mexicana*

Coleoptera apomorphies in hind wing articulation:

AX-PC & C (tegula) reduced; B-R partly membranized; F-M subdivided; B-M large, connected with B-Cu; AX-Cu (3Ax) small, sutured, and often fragmented; AX-Cu fused with F-Cu; F-Cu fused with FA

Trogidae: *Omorgus squalidus*

Trogidae: *Polynoncus mirabilis*

Trogidae: *Trox fascicularis*

Trogidae: *Trox*

